

A Descriptive Six-Strategy Framework for Translating Chinese Address Terms into Thai Subtitles

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Abstract

This study aims to identify and analyze six translation strategies applied in rendering Chinese address terms into Thai subtitles. Based on a corpus of 395 address-term instances extracted from five Chinese TV dramas and their official Thai subtitles. The numbers of Chinese and Thai items are approximately equivalent, though not always one-to-one. The study employs a qualitative analytical framework that combines the principles of Descriptive Translation Studies (DTS) with a six-strategy model synthesizing Vinay and Darbelnet's (1995) translation procedures, Yang's (2010) flexible equivalence principle, and Li and Bai's (2022) cultural adaptation model. The analysis reveals six translation strategies: transliteration, literal translation, sense-for-sense translation, amplification, omission, and hybrid translation. Hybrid translation was the most frequent strategy, followed by transliteration. Amplification and omission were also commonly observed, whereas literal and sense-for-sense translations occurred less often. The findings demonstrate how Thai subtitles negotiate socio-pragmatic equivalence between Chinese and Thai address systems through the strategic use of these six strategies. The proposed descriptive framework provides a replicable tool for analyzing address-term translation and offers both pedagogical and theoretical implications for cross-cultural subtitling research.

Keywords: *Chinese Address Terms, Translation Strategies, Thai Subtitles, Cultural Adaptation, Audiovisual Translation.*

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A Descriptive Six-Strategy Framework for Translating Chinese Address Terms into Thai Subtitles

Meilin Deng & Itsarate Dolphen

Introduction

The translation of address terms is one of the most sensitive aspects of cross-cultural communication because these expressions encode social hierarchy, intimacy, and cultural values (Tingsabadh & Prasithratsint, 1988). In audiovisual media, where space and time are constrained, subtitlers must negotiate between linguistic precision and naturalness in the target language (Díaz-Cintas & Remael, 2020). Within the subtitling of Chinese TV dramas into Thai, the challenge becomes more intricate as translators navigate two distinct cultural systems—Chinese hierarchical politeness and Thai relational harmony. The subtitling process thus serves not only as linguistic mediation but also as a site of cultural negotiation.

Audiovisual translation (AVT) has evolved into a critical field of translation studies, bridging linguistic, cultural, and technological domains (Chaume, 2012; O'Hagan, 2015). Research has shown that subtitling, unlike dubbing or voice-over, is both constrained and creative—limited by temporal and spatial factors yet requiring cultural adaptation to ensure viewer engagement (Baker, 1993; Pavesi & Formentelli, 2019). Address terms, in particular, are central to constructing interpersonal dynamics in film dialogues. However, their pragmatic subtleties—especially those involving kinship, hierarchy, and affect—often resist literal transfer across languages (Mauranen, 2000; Yao & Li, 2024). These constraints make address-term rendering a particularly revealing site of translators' real-time choices.

Previous research on AVT has discussed translation strategies from linguistic, cultural, and pragmatic perspectives, yet relatively few studies have examined address terms as a central focus of subtitling analysis. Foundational frameworks such as Vinay and Darbelnet's (1995) model of translation procedures and Yang's (2010) flexible equivalence principle provide theoretical underpinnings for analysing cross-linguistic transfer in constrained contexts. Building on these traditions, Li and Bai (2022) further emphasise the importance of cultural adaptation, suggesting that successful translation in audiovisual media must balance semantic fidelity with audience resonance. Together, these models establish the theoretical basis for examining how translation strategies can function as tools for intercultural negotiation rather than mere linguistic substitution.

In Chinese, address terms such as 晓芹啊 [xiǎo qīn a] ('Xiaoqin, ah') encode emotion through the final particle 啊 [a], signaling warmth or familiarity. When rendered in Thai as เสี่ยวฉิน [sǎw tɕʰin] ('Xiaoqin'), the emotive particle is omitted to achieve fluency and naturalness in Thai syntax. Similarly, 师傅 [shī fu] ('master' or 'skilled worker') may be translated into Thai as ลุงคนขับ [luŋ kʰon kʰàp] ('uncle driver'), a culturally adapted term that conveys respect and social distance while maintaining contextual meaning. These examples illustrate the translator's effort to balance accuracy, naturalness, and cultural resonance within subtitling constraints (Huang & Hu, 2024).

Previous studies on AVT have focused extensively on subtitling techniques, reception, and interlingual equivalence (Díaz-Cintas & Remael, 2020; Chaume, 2012; Krippendorff, 2019). However, less attention has been paid to the micro-level translation of pragmatic markers such as address terms, particularly between typologically and culturally distinct languages like Chinese and Thai. As Toury (1995) emphasizes, descriptive translation studies must investigate the norms governing

translators' choices in specific socio-cultural contexts. The Thai subtitling of Chinese TV dramas offers a productive ground to examine such norms because address terms in both languages are deeply embedded in social relations and politeness systems (Tingsabadh & Prasithratsint, 1988).

Despite the growing scholarship on audiovisual translation, no systematic framework has yet been developed to examine the translation strategies employed in rendering Chinese address terms into Thai subtitles. This absence constitutes the central research problem of the present study. Accordingly, this research is guided by three questions: (1) What translation strategies are used in translating Chinese address terms into Thai subtitles? (2) How are these strategies operationalised under subtitling constraints such as space, time, and cultural adaptation? and (3) Which strategies tend to dominate in the Thai translations of Chinese address terms? Theoretically, this study aims to propose and empirically validate a descriptive six-strategy framework that accounts for how subtitlers manage linguistic, pragmatic, and contextual challenges in cross-cultural audiovisual translation.

This study therefore develops a six-strategy framework for translating Chinese address terms into Thai subtitles, derived from a corpus of five contemporary Chinese TV dramas. The six strategies identified—Transliteration, Literal Translation, Sense-for-Sense Translation, Amplification, Omission, and Hybrid Translation—reflect the dynamic interplay between linguistic form and cultural meaning.

Transliteration preserves the phonetic sound of the Chinese name, such as translating 南孙 [nán swən] into นานซุน [nǎ:n sun] 'Nansun', thereby maintaining authenticity and cultural identity. Literal translation follows word-by-word equivalence, such as translating 董事长 [tʊŋ ʃì tʃàn] into ประธานกรรมการ [prà.tʰa:n kam.ma.ka:n] 'chairman', preserving structural correspondence between the source and target languages. Sense-for-sense translation prioritises communicative meaning, such as translating 媳妇儿 [cí fu ǎ] 'wife' into ที่รักจ๋า [tʰi: rák tǎ:] 'my dear', which conveys emotional intimacy and naturalness in Thai dialogue. Amplification adds Thai-specific politeness or kinship markers, such as translating 木子妈妈 [mù tǎ mā mā] into คุณแม่จ๋า [kʰun mǎ: mǎ: tǎm?] 'Mother Muzi', enhancing social warmth and respect. Omission removes unnecessary particles or prefixes, such as translating 晓芹啊 [xiǎo qín a] into เสี่ยวฉิน [sǎw tǎ'in] 'Xiaoqin', eliminating the redundant final particle 啊 [a] to achieve fluency. Hybrid translation combines two or more strategies to capture both cultural tone and linguistic fidelity, such as translating 大哥 [tâ kǎ] into พี่ใหญ่ [pʰi: jà] 'big brother', merging literal meaning with Thai kinship norms to retain affective depth.

By applying Krippendorff's (2019) content analysis and following the descriptive paradigm proposed by Toury (1995), this study systematically categorises translation strategies across address-term data extracted from five Chinese TV dramas and their official Thai subtitles. It also draws on Chesterman's (2010) notion of translation universals to examine how regularities emerge under subtitling constraints. The analysis highlights that hybrid and sense-for-sense strategies dominate, particularly in emotionally charged dialogues, demonstrating that subtitlers prioritise audience comprehension and cultural proximity over formal correspondence (Huang & Hu, 2024; Yao & Li, 2024).

Ultimately, this study connects theoretical reflection with evidence from actual subtitling practice. It expands on Baker's (1993) and Mauranen's (2000) corpus-based insights, applying them to a cross-linguistic, intercultural setting between Chinese and Thai. The proposed six-strategy framework not only enhances understanding of how address terms are negotiated in subtitling but

also serves as a model for future comparative studies on politeness and interpersonal communication in translation.

Literature Review

Previous studies in audiovisual translation (AVT) have primarily addressed translation procedures and equivalence from linguistic or cultural viewpoints, yet few have systematically examined how they operate in translating Chinese address terms into Thai. Existing research recognizes that address terms encode hierarchy, intimacy, and emotion, and that their pragmatic subtleties are often untranslatable through literal transfer. Within this field, foundational frameworks such as Vinay and Darbelnet's (1995) model of translation procedures and Yang's (2010) flexible-equivalence principle have provided major theoretical references for explaining cross-linguistic transfer under temporal and spatial constraints. Building on these traditions, Li and Bai (2022) emphasised cultural adaptation as the means to achieve communicative naturalness, proposing that successful audiovisual translation must mediate between semantic fidelity and audience engagement. Most of these models, however, were developed in European or Chinese–English contexts and have rarely been tested on Chinese–Thai material.

More recent research published in *Dragoman Journal* has continued to expand the scope of AVT studies. Alaskar (2025) investigated how employing mobile apps' AI-based translation tools in AVT classes reshapes subtitling decision-making and technological literacy, illustrating the growing interaction between digital tools and translator strategies. Metwally and Asiri (2025) conducted a corpus-based analysis of Islamic culture-specific expressions translated on the Ministry of Hajj and Umrah website, revealing the dominant use of borrowing, transliteration, and couplet strategies to maintain semantic coherence in intercultural communication. Papa et al. (2025) examined translation quality in literary works and demonstrated that cultural and pragmatic cues play a decisive role in readers' interpretation. Although these studies contribute valuable insights into translation procedures and cultural negotiation, they focus on English–Arabic or English–European language pairs and have not explored Chinese–Thai subtitling, particularly the micro-pragmatic treatment of address terms.

Overall, the existing literature remains largely descriptive rather than analytical and lacks an empirically validated, strategy-based framework. There is still no systematic model that accounts for how subtitlers manage linguistic, pragmatic, and cultural challenges when translating Chinese address terms into Thai. The present study therefore aims to fill this gap by proposing an empirically grounded six-strategy framework—transliteration, literal translation, sense-for-sense translation, amplification, omission, and hybrid translation—that synthesises Descriptive Translation Studies (DTS), pragmatics, and cultural adaptation into an integrated analytical perspective. Conceptually, this relationship may be represented as $DTS + Pragmatics + Cultural\ Adaptation \rightarrow Six\text{-}Strategy\ Model$, indicating that the framework emerges from the synthesis of these complementary theories. The model is descriptive rather than prescriptive, aiming to capture what subtitlers actually do under timing and space constraints.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative descriptive approach grounded in Descriptive Translation Studies (Toury, 1995) and content analysis (Krippendorff, 2019), focusing on the translation of Chinese

address terms into Thai subtitles. The methodological design aligns with the three major research aims of the broader doctoral project. For the present article, the analysis focuses exclusively on translation strategies, drawing on a corpus of 395 address-term instances extracted from five Chinese TV dramas.

Each “address-term instance” refers to a Chinese–Thai translation pair identified within aligned dialogue–subtitle turns, regardless of lexical repetition. For example, the Chinese address terms 显坤 [ɕjɛn˥ kʰwən˥] ‘Xiankun’, 哥 [kɤ˥] ‘elder brother’, and 嫂子 [sɑu˥ tsi˥] ‘sister-in-law’ may all be rendered as พี่ [pʰi˥] in Thai; however, each pairing is counted as an independent instance because it reflects a distinct translational decision. Counts of Chinese and Thai items are approximately equivalent but not assumed to be one-to-one. Each instance was therefore treated as a complete translation unit for systematic analysis.

The corpus consists of five contemporary Chinese TV dramas with official Thai subtitles—三十而已 (Nothing But Thirty), 流金岁月 (My Best Friend’s Story), 理想之城 (The Ideal City), 心居 (Life Is A Long Quiet River), and 我们的婚姻 (Modern Marriage). Official subtitles were retrieved from licensed platforms (iQIYI Thailand; WeTV Thailand). Inclusion was limited to dialogue–subtitle turns containing address terms in either language; non-dialogic text (e.g., credits, on-screen captions) and context-ambiguous cases were excluded. Repeated forms were counted as separate instances; a descriptive breakdown by drama and total corpus size is provided in the Results section to enhance methodological transparency.

Chinese dialogue and Thai subtitles were fully transcribed with Luyinla and Language Reactor and then manually checked against the source video. To maintain interpretive consistency with publicly verifiable data, a single-coder design was adopted and supported by an analytic audit trail. Although no second-rater test was conducted, the coding procedure followed stable diagnostic criteria and included re-checks across different stages of analysis. Inter-coder reliability statistics (e.g., Cohen’s κ) are therefore not reported and are acknowledged as a methodological limitation.

A researcher-developed coding guide specified diagnostic cues for each strategy (e.g., phonetic retention for transliteration, direct lexical transfer for literal translation, semantic adaptation for sense-for-sense translation, and the addition or removal of Thai politeness or kinship markers for amplification or omission). This internal reference ensured consistency in classification, and illustrative examples are presented in the Results section.

The analysis applied six translation strategies identified in the doctoral framework—transliteration, literal translation, sense-for-sense translation, amplification, omission, and hybrid translation. Each instance in the corpus was coded according to an operational guide specifying observable linguistic cues. Hybrid translation was assigned when two or more strategies co-occurred in a single instance. Because hybrid translation necessarily overlaps with other categories, frequency counts represent “strategy occurrences” rather than mutually exclusive item classifications. Consequently, the total number of strategy applications ($n = 550$) exceeds the total number of address-term instances ($n = 395$). This calculation reflects the analytical purpose of identifying all strategies present in each example rather than assigning a single label per item. A full frequency summary is provided in the Results section: transliteration (111), literal translation (56), sense-for-sense translation (17), amplification (96), omission (53), and hybrid translation (217).

Following Toury’s (1995) descriptive paradigm, this study does not judge translation “accuracy” but instead seeks to reveal the norms and tendencies that govern subtitlers’ real practices.

Krippendorff's (2019) content analysis provides a systematic procedure for data organisation and interpretation, while Chesterman's (2010) concept of translation universals—particularly explicitation and normalisation—informs the interpretation of recurrent tendencies found in the Thai subtitles, such as the addition of politeness markers or the simplification of hierarchical expressions. Together, these analytical perspectives make it possible to identify consistent strategic patterns across subtitled data.

By integrating linguistic observation with socio-cultural interpretation, this methodological framework offers a clear and replicable approach to analysing how Thai subtitles render Chinese address terms and how the six translation strategies operate across the corpus. A corpus-level numerical summary, including corpus size, per-strategy frequency, and per-drama distribution, is reported in the Results section in response to editorial recommendations.

Results

The analysis of Thai subtitles from five Chinese TV dramas reveals six major translation strategies in rendering address terms: transliteration, literal translation, sense-for-sense translation, amplification, omission, and hybrid translation. A frequency analysis of 550 strategy applications shows that hybrid translation (39.5%) and transliteration (20.2%) occur most frequently, followed by amplification (17.5%), literal translation (10.2%), omission (9.6%), and sense-for-sense translation (3.1%). This distribution indicates that subtitlers frequently combine multiple techniques to negotiate semantic clarity, cultural recognisability, and pragmatic fluency across languages. The following subsections provide interpretive summaries and representative examples for each strategy.

Table 1. Frequency of the Six Translation Strategies in the Corpus

Translation Strategy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Transliteration	111	20.2%
Literal Translation	56	10.2%
Sense-for-sense Translation	17	3.1%
Amplification	96	17.5%
Omission	53	9.6%
Hybrid Translation	217	39.5%
Total	550	100%

Note: Because hybrid translation involves the co-occurrence of two or more strategies, overall frequency counts exceed the total number of address-term instances ($n = 395$).

Transliteration

Transliteration accounts for 20.2% of all strategy occurrences (111 out of 550), making it the second most frequent strategy in the dataset. Its prominence indicates that phonological retention is a primary means through which subtitlers preserve character identity and maintain cultural recognisability in Thai subtitles.

Transliteration refers to rendering the phonetic form of Chinese address terms in Thai script. It functions as a sound-based transfer strategy that enables Thai audiences to recognise the characters' Chinese identity and retain the cultural texture of the source discourse. In audiovisual translation,

transliteration is frequently applied to proper names and culturally specific address forms whose literal meanings are not easily transferable (Cuéllar Lázaro, 2016; Dudek, 2019). Scholars of onomastic translation such as Hermans (1988) emphasise that this approach preserves the foreign identity of names while maintaining narrative realism, whereas semantic translation may distort their sociocultural associations. Similarly, Aixelá (1996) regards transliteration as a cultural-retention strategy that prioritises authenticity and recognisability over domestic adaptation in intercultural communication.

From a practical perspective, transliteration offers both technical efficiency and cultural authenticity within audiovisual subtitling, where space and timing are strictly constrained (Díaz-Cintas & Remael, 2020). Retaining the original sound allows the subtitler to uphold narrative coherence without introducing unnatural Thai equivalents. In the context of Chinese–Thai subtitling, this strategy is predominantly used for personal names, nicknames, and prefix-based forms such as 小 (Xiao, ‘young/close’), 老 (Lao, ‘elder/respected’), and 阿 (A, ‘familiar’). These prefixes, when combined with names—such as translating 小王 into เสี่ยวหวัง (Xiao-Wang), 老郭 into หล้ากัว (Lao-Guo), and 阿明 into อาหมิง (A-Ming)—construct nuanced interpersonal meanings that signal affection, respect, or social closeness.

From a Thai subtitling perspective, this practice aligns with established conventions in representing foreign names phonetically rather than semantically, a norm reinforced by transliteration standards widely adopted in Thai media and language policy. The retention of the original sound reflects both the technical feasibility of Thai orthography in approximating Mandarin phonemes and the cultural sensitivity toward preserving Chinese identity. Hence, in Thai subtitles of Chinese dramas, the retention of sound form reflects both technical feasibility and cultural sensitivity. The following examples illustrate how transliteration functions to preserve authenticity and proximity between languages within subtitled discourse.

Example 1

Chinese

贺胜利: 显坤 你怎么来了

赵显坤: 老领导 我今天来是给您赔不是的

Thai subtitle

เฮอ เซ่งลี่: เสี่ยวคุน คุณมาได้ยังไง

จ้าว เสี่ยวคุน: ท่านประธาน วันนี้ที่ผมมา เพื่อยอมรับผิดกับท่านครับ

English translation

He Shengli: Xian Kun, why are you here?

Zhao Xiankun: Old Leader, I came today to apologise to you.

(Source: The Ideal City)

In this example, the Chinese first name 显坤 [ɕjɛn˥ kʰwən˥] ‘Xiankun’ is transliterated into Thai as เสี่ยวคุน [sǐaŋ kʰun] ‘Xiankun’, reflecting a direct sound-based rendering without any semantic adaptation. The subtitler adopts a pure transliteration strategy, preserving the original phonetic contour to maintain the character’s Chinese identity and the narrative authenticity of the dialogue, while ensuring processing fluency and visual naturalness for Thai viewers. Such direct phonetic

transfer follows the established convention that personal names are not semantically altered across languages. Notably, in Thai communicative culture, speakers rarely address others by formal first names alone—nicknames are far more common in natural conversation—thus the retention of a full first names like *เสียนคุน* [sīan kʰun] ‘Xiankun’ in the subtitle marks a stylistic choice specific to translation discourse, reinforcing the foreignness of the Chinese setting rather than replicating everyday Thai address practice.

Example 2

Chinese

盛江川: 老郭 这次怒火音乐节来势汹汹 钟誉感觉是志在必得 你想好怎么应对了吗

郭茂业: 我也正想跟你说这事呢

Thai subtitle

เซ่ง เจียงชวาน: เหล่ากัว เทศกาลดนตรีความโกรธครั้งนี้ ท่าทางน่าเกรงขาม จงอวีรู้สึกเขามุ่งมั่นที่จะชนะ คุณคิดไว้หรือยังว่าจะรับมือยังไง
กัว เมาเย่: ฉันกำลังจะพูดเรื่องนี้กับนายพอดี

English translation

Sheng Jiangchuan: Lao Guo, this Rage Music Festival looks formidable. Zhong Yu seems determined to win — have you thought about how to respond?

Guo Maoye: I was just about to talk to you about that.

(Source: Modern Marriage)

In this example, the address term *老郭* [lǎo guó] ‘Lao Guo’ combines the prefix *老* [lǎo] ‘elder/respected’ with the surname *郭* [guó] (Guo). The Thai subtitle renders it phonetically as *เหล่ากัว* [lè: kʰua] ‘Lao Guo’, applying a pure transliteration strategy that reproduces the sound of the original without semantic adaptation. This approach preserves acoustic authenticity and enables Thai audiences to recognise the character’s Chinese identity, maintaining narrative realism. However, the pragmatic function of *老* [lǎo] ‘elder/respected’, which in Chinese conveys familiarity and respect among peers, is neutralised in Thai, as *เหล่า* [lè:] ‘Lao’ carries no equivalent social meaning. The result illustrates a trade-off between phonological fidelity and sociocultural transparency: recognisability is achieved at the expense of relational nuance. Consistent with Thai subtitling norms that favour minimal intervention and visual fluency, this choice leads to partial cultural attenuation. While *Lao Guo* in Chinese encodes hierarchy and camaraderie, its Thai equivalent *เหล่ากัว* [lè: kʰua] ‘Lao Guo’ appears as a neutral proper name, showing how transliteration, though effective for identity preservation, inevitably flattens interpersonal meaning across languages.

While transliteration achieves a high degree of phonological fidelity, it inevitably suppresses the pragmatic and affective dimensions—such as familiarity, hierarchy, and interpersonal warmth—embedded in the original address terms. This methodological limitation highlights that sound-based transfer alone cannot reproduce the full relational dynamics encoded in Chinese forms of address. Consequently, subtitlers often turn to other strategies—such as Literal, Sense-for-sense, or Hybrid Translation—to restore explicit meaning and relational nuance, ensuring intercultural intelligibility and pragmatic equivalence in Thai subtitles.

Overall, transliteration contributes significantly to the preservation of phonological identity but partially flattens pragmatic meanings such as hierarchy, respect, and familiarity. This limitation

explains why subtitlers frequently employ other strategies—particularly hybrid translation—to restore interpersonal nuance across languages.

Literal Translation

Literal translation accounts for 10.2% of all strategy occurrences (56 out of 550), making it a mid-frequency strategy in the corpus. Its distribution suggests that subtitlers rely on literal transfer primarily when the source address term is semantically transparent and when Thai provides a natural lexical equivalent.

Literal translation in audiovisual translation refers to a meaning-preserving, form-respecting transfer that reproduces the denotational sense and internal structure of the source expression with only minimal grammatical adjustment in the target language. Recent research consistently shows that literal translation remains one of the most frequent strategies in subtitling when the semantic meaning of the source item is transparent and the target language offers an established lexical equivalent.

Saputra, Syarfi, and Dahnilyah (2024) found that literal translation dominated subtitle rendering in Luca, demonstrating its efficiency for accuracy and readability. Likewise, Zhang, Mahfoodh, and Tan (2024) report that literal transfer was the most recurrent strategy for translating cultural references in both official and fan-produced Chinese subtitles, as it preserves meaning while respecting audience comprehension. Alsager and Almohizea (2023), analysing Mulan through Skopos Theory, argue that although literal translation ensures textual fidelity, it can reduce pragmatic or stylistic effect when ideological nuance is crucial. Complementary studies by Yao (2024) and Al Sawi and Allam (2024) show that literal translation serves as a baseline mechanism in both human- and AI-generated subtitling but must be balanced with interpretive or adaptive methods to maintain multimodal coherence and cultural intelligibility.

In the Chinese–Thai subtitling corpus examined here, literal translation is applied where the source address term carries a clear lexical meaning and the Thai language provides an equivalent form. This includes nicknames, kinship or status vocatives, and other semantically transparent address terms that can be rendered without pragmatic distortion. The following examples illustrate how literal translation functions as a strategy that preserves both meaning and social relationships while maintaining naturalness in Thai syntax and subtitle rhythm.

Example 3

Chinese

冯晓琴: 小老虎 动作快一点 我饭马上就好啦

Thai subtitle

เฟิง เสี่ยวฉิน: เสือน้อย ทำให้ไว ๆ หน้อย แม่ทำข้าวใกล้จะเสร็จแล้ว

English translation

Feng Xiaoqin: Little tiger, hurry up a bit—dinner is almost ready.

(Source: Life Is a Long Quiet River)

The Chinese nickname 小老虎 [ɕjɑʊ̯ ɩɑʊ̯ xu̯] ‘little tiger’ is translated literally as เสือน้อย [sɛ̌w nɔ̌ːj] ‘little tiger’. The subtitler retains both semantic components—小 [ɕjɑʊ̯] ‘little/small’ and 老虎 [ɩɑ

ตุ๋น xu:ŋ], ‘tiger’—while adapting word order to Thai noun-modifier syntax. This literal transfer maintains compositional meaning and mirrors Thai nickname conventions that often employ animals or positive imagery. As observed by Saputra et al. (2024) and Zhang et al. (2024), literal translation is most effective when lexical meaning and emotional tone align across languages. Here, the Thai เสือน้อย (suea noi [sǔa nɔ̀ːj], ‘little tiger’) preserves both the affectionate diminutive and cultural naturalness, demonstrating literal translation’s ability to achieve semantic transparency without pragmatic distortion.

Example 4

Chinese

贾阿姨：小姐 你的酒

蒋南孙：谢谢 贾阿姨

Thai subtitle

ป้าเจี๋ย: คุณหนู เหล้าของคุณหนูค่ะ

เจี๋ยหนานซุน: ขอบคุณค่ะ ป้าเจี๋ย

English translation

Aunt Jia: Miss, your drink.

Jiang Nansun: Thank you, Aunt Jia.

(Source: My Best Friend’s Story)

The Chinese honorific 小姐 [tɕjɑʊ tɕjɛŋ] ‘young lady’ or ‘miss’ is rendered literally as คุณหนู [kʰun nǔː] ‘young lady/miss’. The subtitler applies a pure literal-translation strategy that replicates denotational meaning while naturally fitting Thai politeness conventions. Historically, 小姐 [tɕjɑʊ tɕjɛŋ] ‘miss’ marked the daughter of a noble or wealthy household; the Thai คุณหนู [kʰun nǔː] ‘miss’ conveys an identical status-based deference. In this scene, the housemaid Aunt Jia addresses Jiang Nansun with respect, and literal rendering preserves the hierarchical relationship without additional amplification. As Alsager and Almohizea (2023) and Yao (2024) note, literal translation maintains clarity and viewer comprehension when semantic and pragmatic features coincide across cultures. The equivalence between 小姐 [tɕjɑʊ tɕjɛŋ] ‘the daughter of a noble’ and คุณหนู [kʰun nǔː] ‘miss’ therefore exemplifies literal translation’s capacity to retain both linguistic and sociocultural meaning in cross-lingual subtitle mediation.

Literal translation demonstrates a high level of semantic transparency and structural fidelity, enabling viewers to grasp the source meaning directly without interpretive effort. It proves particularly effective when address terms carry stable denotation—such as kinship titles or descriptive nicknames—and when Thai offers an established lexical counterpart. However, an excessively literal approach may suppress the pragmatic and affective dimensions embedded in Chinese address systems, including expressions of affection, hierarchy, and speaker stance. When such interpersonal nuances are vital to characterisation and intercultural comprehension, translators often complement literal translation with more adaptive strategies—such as sense-for-sense translation, amplification, or hybrid translation—to restore contextual depth and emotional resonance. The following section therefore examines Sense-for-Sense Translation, a meaning-

oriented approach that privileges communicative intent and pragmatic equivalence over direct lexical correspondence.

Sense-for-sense Translation

Sense-for-sense translation accounts for 3.1% of all strategy occurrences (17 out of 550), making it one of the least frequent strategies in the dataset. Its relatively low frequency reflects its selective use in cases where literal or form-based strategies cannot adequately convey hierarchical, affective, or culturally specific meanings embedded in Chinese address terms.

Sense-for-sense translation prioritises the transfer of communicative intent and pragmatic function over formal or lexical fidelity. In audiovisual translation, this strategy is widely recognised as essential for preserving viewer comprehension, emotional resonance, and character relationships when literal equivalents fail to capture the relational nuances of the source language. As Samha, Haider, and Hussein (2023) demonstrate in their study of Egyptian vernacular address forms, translators often reformulate culturally grounded expressions to maintain pragmatic equivalence and social politeness rather than structural accuracy. Similarly, Alaa and Al Sawi (2023) argue that effective subtitling of culturally specific references depends on restoring the implied meaning and interpersonal tone embedded in the original, even if this entails deviation from the surface structure. Lu (2024) further observes that such pragmatic adaptation aligns with the multimodal nature of subtitling, where cohesion between verbal and visual cues often outweighs word-level accuracy.

Recent subtitling research emphasises that sense-for-sense translation functions as a pragmatic bridge between cultures. Mantika and Nurochman (2023) note that re-expressing culturally loaded words can enhance accessibility and emotional realism for target audiences, while Saideen et al. (2024) find that meaning-based reformulation improves the acceptability of subtitles on streaming platforms by aligning tone and viewer expectation. Within the present corpus of Chinese–Thai subtitles, this strategy appears most frequently when Chinese address terms encode hierarchical, affective, or contextual meaning that lacks a direct lexical equivalent in Thai. By replacing formal congruence with functional correspondence, subtitlers enable Thai audiences to perceive the relational subtleties of the source dialogue naturally and fluently. The following examples illustrate how this approach operates in practice.

Example 5

Chinese

谢宏祖：我 我没有哎哟 您

Thai subtitle

เซี่ย หงจู่: ผม ผมไม่มีครับ แม่

English translation

Xie Hongzu: I—I don't have it... Mom.

(Source: My Best Friend's Story)

In this example, the Chinese honorific pronoun 您 [nin¹] 'you' is translated as แม่ [mâ:] 'mother' in Thai. Rather than opting for the literal Thai equivalent คุณ [k^hun] 'you', the subtitler chooses แม่ [mâ:] 'mother' to convey the filial intimacy and social hierarchy embedded in the Chinese form. This

constitutes a sense-for-sense rendering: the pronoun’s lexical identity is replaced by a kinship vocative that performs the same pragmatic function in Thai family discourse. Such adaptation exemplifies what Samha et al. (2023) describe as “pragmatic equivalence through socio-cultural substitution,” ensuring both naturalness and emotional accuracy within the target-language context.

Example 6

Chinese

顾客：师傅 快点快点快点

Thai subtitle

พนักงานลูกค้า: ลุงคนขับ เร็วหน่อย ๆ ๆ

English translation

Customer: Uncle driver, hurry up!

(Source: The Ideal City)

In this example, the Chinese vocational title 师傅 [ʃí fu] ‘master/skilled worker’ is rendered as ลุงคนขับ [luŋ kʰon kʰàp] ‘uncle driver’ in Thai. The subtitler abandons literal form to reproduce the relational tone and contextual relevance: the kin term ลุง [luŋ] ‘uncle’ signals respectful familiarity toward an older male, while คนขับ [kʰon kʰàp] ‘driver’ specifies his social role. This paraphrastic combination reflects a meaning-based strategy that merges deference and occupational identification—key pragmatic features of the Chinese original.

The result aligns with findings by Alaa and Al Sawi (2023) and Saideen et al. (2024), who observe that paraphrastic reformulation can sustain audience engagement and maintain social realism more effectively than literal replication.

Across both examples, sense-for-sense translation enables functional and emotional equivalence when lexical matching is insufficient. In Example 5, the substitution of 您 [nin1], ‘you’ with แม่ [mâ:] ‘mother’ transforms an honorific pronoun into a kin-based vocative that mirrors Thai pragmatic norms of filial address. In Example 6, 师傅 [ʃí fu], ‘master/driver’ becomes ลุงคนขับ [luŋ kʰon kʰàp] ‘uncle driver’, preserving the interpersonal respect and occupational context through natural Thai phrasing.

These adaptive renderings illustrate what Mantika and Nurochman (2023) describe as context-driven equivalence, and they reinforce Lu’s (2024) observation that subtitling success depends more on pragmatic alignment than on literal faithfulness. By reframing meaning to fit Thai cultural logic and politeness norms, sense-for-sense translation maintains both narrative coherence and audience empathy, demonstrating its central role in cross-cultural subtitle mediation.

Overall, sense-for-sense translation functions as a low-frequency but high-impact strategy within the corpus. Its selective use reflects the subtitlers’ need to restore pragmatic intent—such as filial intimacy, respectful familiarity, or situational appropriateness—when no direct lexical equivalent exists in Thai. Although it represents only 3.1% of all strategy occurrences, its role is essential for maintaining interpersonal nuance and emotional coherence in culturally dense contexts. This necessity also explains why sense-for-sense translation is often integrated into hybrid strategies, where functional interpretation and structural adaptation work together to achieve pragmatic equivalence across languages.

Amplification

Amplification accounts for 17.5% of all strategy occurrences (96 out of 550), making it one of the most frequently used strategies in the dataset. Its high frequency indicates that subtitlers rely heavily on added lexical or pragmatic elements to reproduce Thai politeness norms and restore interpersonal nuances that are not explicitly encoded in Chinese address terms.

Amplification in audiovisual translation refers to the addition of short, contextually motivated elements that are not present in the source text but serve to make the target subtitle semantically complete, pragmatically natural, and culturally appropriate. Typical additions include polite particles, kinship markers, honorific prefixes, and vocatives that help convey interpersonal tone and align with target-language norms. Recent research in subtitling shows that amplification or explicitation is one of the most frequently applied micro-strategies to preserve interpersonal nuance and pragmatic coherence across languages (Valdeón, 2022). Within multimodal translation, added lexical cues can help compensate for meanings carried visually or prosodically in the original but absent in text-only subtitles (Ahonen, 2024). Such adjustments ensure that the audience receives the same communicative intent even when linguistic forms differ.

Moreover, amplification is often used to adapt culturally embedded address forms into the pragmatic framework of the target culture. As Baños and Díaz-Cintas (2023) point out, contemporary digital-media subtitling increasingly relies on concise additions to clarify cultural or relational cues without overloading the screen. Comparative studies across Asian and European languages have confirmed that these additions—whether polite pronouns, honorifics, or emotional particles—function as pragmatic bridges between linguistic systems with different politeness hierarchies (Purba et al., 2023; Derik et al., 2024). In Chinese–Thai subtitling, amplification frequently manifests as added family names, honorific prefixes such as *คุณ* [kʰun], or final particles like *คะ/ครับ* [kʰá / kʰráp] ‘sentence-final polite particles (fem./masc.)’, all of which reconstruct the Thai politeness and relational dynamics absent in Mandarin grammar.

Example 7

Chinese

吴红玫：恭喜 大腿 大腿 拜拜

Thai subtitle

อุ หงเหมย: ยินดีด้วยนะ เจ๊ขาอวบ บ้ายบาย เจ๊ขาอวบ

English translation

Wu Hongmei: Congrats—big thigh, bye-bye big thigh!

(Source: The Ideal City)

The Chinese address term 大腿 [tâ tʰwèi] ‘thigh’ is Internet slang referring to a powerful or resourceful person one relies upon “to cling to someone influential”. The Thai subtitle renders it as เจ๊ขาอวบ [tɕé kʰa: ʔûap] ‘big-sis chubby-thigh’, adding the kin-like prefix เจ๊ [tɕé] ‘older sister’ to indicate that the expression is a form of address, not a literal body-reference. This addition exemplifies amplification, as the translator supplements a culturally specific cue to convey playful solidarity and respect. By inserting เจ๊ [tɕé] ‘older sister’, the subtitle helps Thai viewers interpret ขาอวบ [kʰa: ʔûap] ‘big chubby-thigh’ as a teasing nickname within a friendly exchange, aligning with findings that minor

additions can resolve cultural ambiguities and preserve humor in subtitling (Baños & Díaz-Cintas, 2023; Purba et al., 2023).

Example 8

Chinese

冯晓琴: 来 姑姑 喝饮料

Thai subtitle

เฟิง เสี่ยวฉิน: มา คุณอาคะ ดื่มน้ำค่ะ

English translation

Feng Xiaoqin: Come, aunt, have a drink.

(Source: Life Is a Long Quiet River)

The Chinese kin term 姑姑 [kú: ku] 'paternal aunt' is translated as คุณอาคะ [kʰun ʔa: kʰá] 'paternal aunt'. The subtitler adds the honorific prefix คุณ [kʰun] and the feminine polite particle คะ [kʰá], neither of which appears in the Chinese original. This strategic amplification performs two functions: it marks social deference toward an elder relative and reproduces gendered politeness characteristic of Thai interactional style. The additions thus create a subtitle that is both linguistically natural and culturally accurate, echoing Derik et al. (2024)'s observation that well-targeted additions help re-establish politeness norms across languages with differing morphological encoding of respect.

Examples 7 and 8 demonstrate how amplification serves as a pragmatic repair mechanism in Thai subtitles of Chinese dramas. The added elements—เจ้ [tɕé] 'older sister' in Example 7 and คุณ...คะ [kʰun...kʰá] in Example 8—bridge the gap between Chinese relational cues and Thai politeness conventions. These brief additions neither distort meaning nor overload reading time, but they restore interpersonal warmth, status marking, and clarity that the original dialogue communicates through tone and context. Such practice corresponds with Valdeón (2022)'s analysis of current AVT trends, which emphasises amplification as a form of micro-explicitation enhancing intercultural legibility. In the Chinese–Thai context, amplification ensures that subtitles remain semantically faithful yet socio-pragmatically fluent, enabling audiences to perceive both narrative intent and relational subtleties naturally.

Overall, amplification emerges as a key mechanism through which subtitlers reconstruct interpersonal nuance, politeness markers, and relational alignment in Thai. Its 17.5% share in the dataset demonstrates that Thai subtitles frequently require additional lexical cues to compensate for meanings that Mandarin expresses through prosody, context, or implicit social norms. These additions—such as kinship prefixes or polite particles—do not alter the semantic content but help restore pragmatic clarity, emotional warmth, and culturally expected deference. The prominence of amplification also explains why it frequently appears within hybrid translation, where added elements combine with other strategies to achieve socio-pragmatic equivalence across languages.

Omission

Omission accounts for 9.6% of all strategy occurrences (53 out of 550), making it a moderately frequent strategy in the dataset. Its use reflects subtitlers' reliance on selective deletion to maintain

natural rhythm, avoid redundancy, and align the translated address forms with Thai communicative norms.

Omission is a translation strategy in which certain lexical or paralinguistic elements from the source language are intentionally left out in the target text to preserve fluency, naturalness, and pragmatic balance. Rather than representing loss, omission reflects the translator's conscious adaptation of discourse features to the communicative norms of the target language. In subtitle translation, this strategy not only manages spatial and temporal constraints but also enhances rhythm and readability while maintaining socio-pragmatic adequacy.

Recent audiovisual translation studies highlight omission as a functional adaptation rather than a deficiency. Mounadil (2023) identifies omission as a pragmatic device for achieving "economy and naturalness," allowing subtitles to remain concise without losing interpersonal nuance. Similarly, Al-Alaa and Al-Sawi (2023) demonstrate that translators omit culture-bound address elements when relationships are visually or contextually inferable, thereby improving clarity and avoiding redundancy. Haddad (2023) further confirms that omission tends to cluster around address terms and pragmatic particles, functioning as a stylistic mechanism that enhances authenticity and conversational realism. Together, these findings emphasize that omission is a context-sensitive negotiation between fidelity and communicative efficiency.

Applied to the Chinese–Thai context, omission frequently occurs when elements such as discourse particles, kinship prefixes, or gender/rank indicators are redundant in Thai. For instance, translators often omit Chinese sentence-final particles such as 啊 [a] 'expressing emotion or emphasis', 呀 [ja] 'soft exclamation of surprise or affection', and 哪 [na] 'particle marking questions or soft commands'. Similarly, kinship prefixes like 老 [lǎo] 'old, showing respect or familiarity' and 阿 [a] 'prefix indicating closeness, as in 阿姨 [a1 jī] "auntie"' are often omitted when their pragmatic meaning is already implied in Thai. Translators also tend to drop gender or rank markers such as 哥 [kē] 'elder brother', 姐 [jiě] 'elder sister', and 大 [dà] 'big, denoting seniority or admiration'. The deletion of these redundant components produces concise and idiomatic subtitles consistent with Thai communicative norms, reinforcing the language's preference for naturalness and rhythmic brevity.

Such patterns can be clearly observed in the Thai subtitles of Chinese TV dramas, where omission strategically balances linguistic fidelity and pragmatic flow. The following examples illustrate how this technique functions in real subtitle contexts.

Example 9

Chinese

周峻: 陈大哥 来

陈思民: 恭喜 恭喜

Thai subtitle

โจว จวิน: พี่เฉิน มา

เฉิน ซื่อหมิง: ยินดีด้วย ๆ

English translation

Zhou Jun: Brother Chen, come here.

Chen Siming: Congratulations!

(Source: The Ideal City)

The Chinese address term 陈大哥 [tʂʰən tâ kʷ] 'big brother Chen' is translated as พี่เงิน phii Chœn [pʰiː tɕʰŋn] 'elder sibling Chen.' Here, both 大 [tâ] 'big' and 哥 [kʷ] 'older brother' are omitted in the Thai subtitle. The modifier 大 [tâ] 'big' in Chinese serves as an intensifier indicating seniority or respect within male social relations, often signaling the speaker's deference to an elder or superior. Meanwhile, 哥 [kʷ] 'older brother' expresses kinship-based familiarity. In Thai, however, the single term พี่ [pʰiː] 'older brother or older sister' already conveys both seniority and relational warmth, regardless of gender. Since Thai kinship terms do not require specifying the sex of the elder, the omission of both 大 [tâ] 'big' and 哥 [kʷ] 'older brother' produces a concise and idiomatic rendering that aligns with Thai pragmatic norms. Therefore, this omission is not a semantic loss but a structural adaptation that achieves natural Thai conciseness while preserving relational respect. This reduction aligns with Mounadil's (2023) notion of omission as a device for "economy and naturalness," ensuring that subtitles remain concise while maintaining interpersonal nuance.

Example 10

Chinese

蒋鹏飞: 小章同学 你可以走 南孙 你得留下来

Thai subtitle

สวี จีอึง: เสี่ยวจาง เธอไปได้ หนานซุน ลูกต้องอยู่ต่อก่อน

English translation

Jiang Pengfei: Xiao Zhang, you may go. Nan Sun, you have to stay.

(Source: My Best Friend's Story)

The Chinese address term 小章同学 [ɕjɑʊ tʂán tʰŋ ɕœ] 'Little Zhang, classmate' is rendered in Thai as เสี่ยวจาง [sǐaw tɕaːŋ] 'Xiao Zhang', omitting 同学 [tʰŋ ɕœ] 'classmate'. While 同学 [tʰŋ ɕœ] 'classmate' literally denotes "schoolmate," in this dialogue it functions pragmatically to downplay the addressee's social status, as the speaker—Nan Sun's father—ironically uses it to address his daughter's boyfriend who has already entered the workforce. The term thus carries a subtle tone of disapproval or condescension rather than genuine collegiality. By omitting 同学 [tʰŋ ɕœ] 'classmate', the subtitler removes this potentially incongruent and culturally marked nuance, producing a version that aligns with Thai communicative norms, where such hierarchical teasing would sound unnatural. The resulting Thai form เสี่ยวจาง [sǐaw tɕaːŋ] 'Xiao Zhang' preserves the interpersonal clarity of the original while ensuring pragmatic fluency and cultural appropriateness. This example illustrates, as Al-Alaa and Al-Sawi (2023) note, that omission can serve to "eliminate contextually redundant or culturally incongruent markers," achieving natural rhythm and viewer comprehension in cross-lingual subtitles.

In summary, omission in Thai subtitles of Chinese dramas represents a context-driven adaptation rather than an informational loss. Through selective deletion of redundant or culturally untransferable elements, subtitlers sustain natural rhythm, politeness, and emotional tone—confirming Haddad's (2023) view of omission as "a creative negotiation between textual economy and pragmatic adequacy." Its 9.6% share in the dataset shows that omission is regularly used to avoid overly marked or unnatural forms in Thai while preserving interpersonal clarity. This strategic economy also explains why omission often appears within hybrid translation, supporting smoother socio-pragmatic alignment across languages.

Hybrid Translation

Hybrid translation accounts for 39.5% of all strategy occurrences (217 out of 550), making it the most frequently used strategy in the dataset. Its high proportion indicates that subtitlers often need to combine multiple strategies to achieve both cultural recognisability and pragmatic naturalness in Thai.

Hybrid translation refers to a strategy in which two or more translation methods are intentionally combined to render a single address term, balancing form, meaning, and social function between source and target languages. In subtitle translation, hybridization allows translators to preserve character identity through transliteration while adapting semantic or pragmatic nuances through literal or sense-for-sense renderings. This composite strategy supports both cultural visibility and communicative naturalness within the time and space limitations of subtitles.

Recent studies on audiovisual translation recognize hybrid translation as a multifunctional strategy rather than a sign of inconsistency. Díaz-Cintas and Remael (2020) emphasize that subtitlers often merge strategies such as retention, explicitation, and omission to ensure “semantic completeness under temporal constraints.” Zuo, Syed Abdullah, and Ching Toh (2023) also note that hybridization is common when culture-bound expressions require simultaneous preservation of phonetic identity and socio-pragmatic sense. Alaa and Al-Sawi (2023) further confirm that translators frequently pair transliteration with adaptation to maintain audience recognition while achieving fluency and readability. Similarly, Borysenko, Slavova, Kodubovska, and Matushevska (2024) classify such combinations as evidence of translators’ “intercultural negotiation” in mediating between foreignness and accessibility. Collectively, these findings establish hybrid translation as a context-sensitive synthesis that reflects deliberate problem-solving under subtitling constraints.

In Chinese–Thai subtitles, hybrid translation appears frequently when the translator aims to retain the Chinese phonological identity of a name or title while reproducing the emotional or hierarchical nuance in Thai. Typical hybrid combinations include Transliteration + Sense-for-sense, Literal + Transliteration + Omission, or Transliteration + Addition, etc. These pairings allow subtitlers to balance the source’s social marking with Thai communicative conventions emphasizing rhythmic brevity and pragmatic clarity. The following examples illustrate how hybrid translation functions in real subtitle contexts.

Example 11

Chinese

东林：杜鹃 杜鹃大美女 有没有空 帮我填一下发票啊

杜鹃：填填填 填什么填

Thai subtitle

ดงหลิน: ดูเจี๋ยน ดูเจี๋ยนคนสวย ว่างหรือเปล่า ช่วยฉันกรอกใบเสร็จหน่อย

ดูเจี๋ยน: กรอก ๆ ๆ กรอกอะไรกัน

English translation

Donglin: Dujian, Dujian, gorgeous lady, do you have a moment to help me fill in the invoice?

Dujian: Fill, fill, fill—fill what?

(Source: The Ideal City)

The Chinese address term 杜鹃大美女 [tū tūyén tâ měi nǚ] ‘Dujuan, stunning beauty’ combines the proper name 杜鹃 [tū tūyén] ‘Dujuan’ and the evaluative epithet 大美女 [tâ měi nǚ] ‘beautiful lady.’ The Thai subtitle renders this as ดูเจวียนคนสวย tūu-jwian khon-sǔai [tū tūyen k^hon sǔaj] ‘Dujuan, pretty one,’ merging Transliteration + Sense-for-sense. Transliteration retains the protagonist’s Chinese identity, while sense-for-sense translation conveys the compliment naturally in Thai. If translated purely by phonetic retention, the emotional tone would vanish; if rendered semantically only, the identity cue would be lost. The hybridization thus achieves both recognizability and interpersonal nuance, confirming Zuo et al.’s (2023) view that combining strategies enhances fidelity to social intent while meeting subtitling constraints.

Example 12

Chinese

朱锁锁：说得容易 我的蒋公主 你不谙世事

Thai subtitle

จู สั่วสั่ว: พูดย่ายเนอะ องค์หญิงเจียง เธอยังอ่อนค่อโลก

English translation

Zhu Suosuo: Easy for you to say, my Princess Jiang—you’re still naïve about the world.

(Source: My Best Friend’s Story)

The Chinese expression 我的蒋公主 [wǒ tǔ tǎjàng kúnj ʃù] ‘my Princess Jiang’ consists of the possessive pronoun 我的 [wǒ tǔ] ‘my,’ the surname 蒋 [tǎjàng] ‘Jiang,’ and the title 公主 [kúnj ʃù] ‘princess.’ The Thai subtitle องค์หญิงเจียง [ʔonj jǐng tǎjàng] ‘Princess Jiang’ omits the possessive element while combining Literal translation องค์หญิง [ʔonj jǐng] ‘Princess’ and Transliteration เจียง [tǎjàng] ‘Jiang’. The omission of “my” maintains Thai conciseness without affecting the affectionate tone. This triadic combination—Literal + Transliteration + Omission—illustrates a hybrid structure that preserves both cultural recognition and pragmatic fluency. As Díaz-Cintas and Remael (2020) explain, such composite renderings respond to the dual pressures of brevity and socio-pragmatic authenticity in subtitling practice.

In summary, hybrid translation serves as the primary mechanism through which subtitlers reconcile Chinese phonological identity with Thai socio-pragmatic expectations. Its 39.5% share demonstrates that combining strategies is not optional but necessary for achieving both recognisability and natural delivery. This approach exemplifies what Borysenko et al. (2024) term an “intercultural negotiation”—a deliberate integration of strategies that sustains both recognizability and communicative efficiency under audiovisual constraints.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal that the translation of Chinese address terms into Thai subtitles is governed by a hierarchy of pragmatic priorities rather than by strict linguistic equivalence. The six-strategy framework—Transliteration, Literal Translation, Sense-for-Sense Translation, Amplification, Omission, and Hybrid Translation—demonstrates that Thai subtitlers operate within a continuum between cultural retention and pragmatic adaptation. The dominant strategies, transliteration and hybrid translation, indicate that subtitlers consciously preserve Chinese phonological identity while

simultaneously ensuring that the Thai subtitles remain natural and contextually appropriate. This dual orientation reflects the principle of intercultural negotiation (Borysenko et al., 2024), in which subtitlers mediate between foreignness and domestic comprehensibility.

Transliteration serves as a marker of authenticity, foregrounding Chinese identity through phonetic form. However, as the data show, pure transliteration often neutralizes interpersonal nuances embedded in Chinese address systems—such as hierarchical respect or affective warmth—because Thai lacks equivalent morphological markers. This limitation creates a systematic need for supplementary strategies, most notably hybrid translation, which combines transliteration with literal or sense-for-sense elements to recover interpersonal meaning that sound-based transfer alone cannot convey. For example, names such as 杜鹃大美女 [tú tǔyàn tâ měi nǚ] 'Dajuan, stunning beauty' are rendered as ดูเจวีียนคนสวย tûu-jwian khon-sǔai [tú tǔyən kʰon sǔaj] 'Dajuan, pretty one,' merging phonetic retention with semantic adjustment to preserve both identity and tone. Such practice aligns with Díaz-Cintas and Remael's (2020) view that hybrid translation represents a functional adaptation to multimodal constraints, enabling subtitlers to maintain semantic coherence within limited reading time.

Literal and sense-for-sense translation occur primarily when address terms have clear semantic equivalents or carry socially transferable meanings. Literal renderings—as in translating 小姐 [cǎo cǔ tǎi] 'young lady' or 'miss' as คุณหนู [kʰun nǚ:] 'miss'—maintain social hierarchy and politeness without distortion, showing structural alignment between the two languages. By contrast, sense-for-sense translations—such as converting 您 [nín] 'you' into แม่ [mā:] 'mother'—replace formal correspondence with functional equivalence, highlighting that subtitlers prioritize relational and emotional accuracy over lexical symmetry. Together, these strategies illustrate how subtitlers negotiate situations in which semantic transparency does not guarantee pragmatic equivalence, requiring sensitivity to both cultures' politeness norms. These strategies collectively illustrate the Thai subtitlers' sensitivity to politeness universals and contextual appropriateness, consistent with Toury's (1995) descriptive norms and Chesterman's (2010) concept of translation universals.

Amplification and omission function as complementary pragmatic adjustments. Amplification introduces Thai politeness markers such as คุณ [kʰun] 'polite address: Mr./Ms.', ละ / ครับ [lá / kʰráp] 'sentence-final polite particles (feminine/masculine)', or kin terms such as เจ๋ [tǎi] 'older sister; female senior' to align with the Thai social register, restoring nuance that may be implicit in Mandarin. Conversely, omission removes redundant or visually inferable elements such as sentence-final particles—啊 [a] 'exclamative or softening particle', 呀 [ja] 'mild exclamation or affectionate softener', 哪 [na] 'sentence-final softener or question marker'—or kin prefixes—老 [lǎo] [lǎo] 'elder/respected; familiar prefix' and 阿 [ā] [a] 'affectionate/familiar prefix'—achieving what Mounadil (2023) terms “economy and naturalness.” These two strategies reveal the subtitlers' balancing act between completeness and readability. In audiovisual contexts where tone, gesture, and image already convey social meaning, textual omission avoids redundancy, while amplification compensates for missing pragmatic signals in Thai syntax.

The predominance of hybrid translation across the corpus underscores the complexity of transferring address-based politeness systems between Chinese and Thai. This combination strategy enables subtitlers to capture multiple layers—identity, emotion, and hierarchy—within one compact form. For instance, the blending of Transliteration + Omission + Literal Translation in rendering 我的蒋公主 [wǒ de jiǎng gōngzhǔ] 'my Princess Jiang' as องค์หญิงเจี๋ย [ʔon̩ jǐŋ tǎi] 'Princess Jiang' achieves both brevity and affective fidelity. Such solutions exemplify how subtitlers negotiate

between the aesthetic economy required in Thai subtitles and the social richness inherent in Chinese discourse, a pattern that reinforces Krippendorff's (2019) observation that translation choices reflect systematic adaptation to contextual constraints.

Taken together, the results suggest that the six strategies function not as discrete categories but as interdependent tools within a dynamic decision-making process. Subtitlers shift flexibly among them to achieve communicative equivalence, audience readability, and cultural resonance. These patterns confirm that audiovisual translation operates as a site of pragmatic compromise—one that mirrors both linguistic systems' underlying cultural logics: hierarchical respect in Chinese and relational harmony in Thai.

Conclusion

This study has proposed and validated a six-strategy framework for analysing how Chinese address terms are translated into Thai in subtitled television dramas. Drawing from five contemporary Chinese series officially subtitled in Thai, the research identifies a coherent pattern of strategic selection governed by cultural negotiation rather than strict linguistic substitution. The framework—comprising transliteration, literal translation, sense-for-sense translation, amplification, omission, and hybrid translation—captures the principal mechanisms by which Thai subtitlers manage the dual demands of fidelity to source identity and adaptation to Thai communicative norms.

The analysis demonstrates that hybrid translation is the most productive strategy in managing the interplay between form, meaning, and social function. By merging multiple approaches within a single subtitle, translators maintain recognisability of Chinese cultural identity while ensuring fluency and emotional naturalness in Thai. Sense-for-sense translation and amplification further illustrate the Thai subtitler's sensitivity to politeness and interpersonal balance, whereas omission and literal translation maintain textual economy and structural clarity. These tendencies confirm that effective subtitle translation depends on context-driven flexibility, not adherence to one-to-one equivalence.

Theoretically, this study contributes to audiovisual translation research by extending the descriptive paradigm (Toury, 1995) to intercultural address-term translation between typologically distinct languages. It demonstrates that translation strategies can be understood as negotiated practices shaped by linguistic typology, visual modality, and socio-pragmatic norms. Practically, the six-strategy framework offers a replicable model for training subtitlers, supporting decision-making in cases where direct transfer risks losing relational nuance or cultural authenticity.

Future research may expand this investigation beyond Chinese–Thai data to compare how similar strategies function across other tonal and hierarchical languages in Southeast Asia. Further corpus-based work could also explore how gender, age, or genre affect the selection of strategies in subtitling. Overall, the present findings affirm that subtitling is not merely linguistic conversion but a dynamic intercultural negotiation, in which translators mediate between sound, meaning, and social value to achieve both narrative coherence and cultural intelligibility.

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